

Supplementary Figures for

Global biogeography of warning colouration in the butterfly *Danaus chrysippus*

Wanzhen Liu, David A. S. Smith, Gayatri Raina, Rowan Stanforth, Ivy Ng'Iru, Piera Ileri,
Dino J. Martins, Ian J. Gordon & Simon H. Martin

Figure S1. Identification of *D. chrysippus* genotypes at the A, B and C loci. For each locus, the three panels indicate (assumed) homozygous dominant, heterozygous and homozygous recessive genotypes. Because heterozygotes cannot be reliably genotyped, in our study we have converted all heterozygotes to A- genotypes, and assumed hardy-Weinberg equilibrium. Individual wing images

show the upperside (left) and underside (right), and images below are from citizen science databases.
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Figure S2. Residual maps for each colour pattern trait of *D. chrysippus* between research and citizen datasets (98 cells for hindwing white; 99 grid cells for forewing tip; 84 cells for ground colour). **a:** Hiding white (A locus), **b:** background colour (B locus), **c:** forewing tip (C locus).

Figure S5. Comparing cline analyses using different grid cell sizes (4x4 '4DB' or 2x2 '2DB' degrees) and transect widths (750km, 450km, 220km) for Transect 3 (Southwest Africa).

Figure S6. Comparing cline analyses using different grid cell sizes (4x4 '4DB' or 2x2 '2DB' degrees) and transect widths (750km, 450km, 220km) for Transect 4 (Northwest Africa).

Figure S7. Correlation matrix showing the distributions of the four environmental variables and correlations between them. Bio01: Annual mean temperature, Bio12: Annual precipitation, Bio20: Annual mean radiation, Bio28: Annual mean moisture index.

Figure S8. Relationships between each of the four environmental variables and the frequency of light/orange background colour genotype (*bb*). Lines show linear regression fits, with shaded bands representing 95% confidence intervals. Data Points are shown with 20% jitter to aid in visual interpretation. Pearson correlation coefficient and p-value were shown in the upper left. Bio01: Annual mean temperature, Bio12: Annual precipitation, Bio20: Annual mean radiation, Bio28: Annual mean moisture index.

Figure S9. Model-averaged parameter estimates from the best-fit GLS model for the effect of environmental variables on the frequency of the light/orange background colour genotype (*bb*). Bands represent 95% confidence intervals. Explanatory variables for which the 95% confidence interval overlaps zero (represented by the vertical dotted line) are considered to have no effect on the response. The bold line is used to accentuate the effect of temperature and solar radiation on the phenotype. Bio01: Annual mean temperature, Bio12: Annual precipitation, Bio20: Annual mean radiation, Bio28: Annual mean moisture index. Bio12 and Bio28 were found to have opposite effects despite being highly correlated with each other (Figure S7). Their high VIF scores ($VIF > 11$) implies that their effect sizes may be overestimated. Models including only one of Bio12 and Bio28 have lower AIC scores than the model excluding both of them (Table S4).

Figure S10. Maps of annual mean temperature (Bio01) (a) and frequency of the light background colour genotype (*bb*) of *D. chrysippus*.

Figure S11. Maps of four environmental variables applied in the GLS analysis.